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on Composite Materials

EFFECT OF ACCELERATED AGEING AND MOISTURE ABSORPTION ON MECHANICAL AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF POLYMER COMPOSITES

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- Overview and context
- Objectives of this research
- Ageing of composites
- Understanding effects of moisture
- Conclusions
- Further investigation

Introduction

Growth in UK
Composite Market
£10,200m by 2030

Image credits: Magma Global

Introduction

A S Maxwell and W R Broughton, "Survey of Long-Term Durability Testing of Composites, Adhesives and Polymers", NPL Report, 2016

Objectives

Project Objectives

Ageing of composites

- Immersion in water bath
 - Use of elevated temperatures to accelerate the uptake of moisture in the composite specimens
- Autoclave exposure
 - Elevated pressures have been used for sub sea applications
- Addition of a pre load to autoclave conditioning
 - How does this affect moisture uptake?

Moisture Uptake

Effect of moisture

- Increase in moisture content of the glass fibre composite over time
- Decrease in T_g with the increasing moisture
 - Tested using dynamic mechanical analysis

Effect of moisture

- Comparison of immersed and autoclave aged specimens

Conclusions

- Moisture uptake in composite specimens has been accelerated via use of water baths and autoclaves
- Pressure did not further accelerate the moisture uptake in comparison to immersion, whereas the application of a pre load significantly increased moisture uptake over the same timescales
- Moisture content decreased glass transition temperature, flexural strength and flexural modulus
- Additional pressure, while at the same moisture content, affected the decrease in flexural properties
 - It is possible that the moisture attacks the interface, more quickly for the autoclave aged specimens compared to the immersed specimens

Further Investigation

- Clarification of interface degradation
 - Recoverability of properties after drying. Do interfacial bonds reform?
 - Testing of resin only to determine matrix and fibre role on moisture ingress and property changes
- Industrial case study
 - Comparison of pristine specimens, accelerated aged specimens and those retrieved from in marine service

Thank you for listening

Any questions?

Sponsors: EPSRC, University of Surrey, NPL and Element

Supervisors: Professor Graham Sims, Dr Tony Maxwell (NPL), Professor Robert Dorey, Professor Steve Ogin, Mrs Charlotte Foreman (University of Surrey), Dr Ing Sabine Frenz (Element)

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